

Design and Fabrication of Advanced Mobility Control Robotic Platform used For Multipurpose Applications

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ABSTRACT

This abstract provides an overview of the final year project report on the Advanced Mobility Control Robotic Platform (AMCRP). The AMCRP aims to meet the demand for adaptable robots in diverse environments by prioritizing advanced mobility and modularity. Featuring multiple locomotion configurations and an advanced control system, it offers versatility for various applications. The development process encompasses conceptual design, system design, prototyping, testing, and refinement. With potential applications in search and rescue, logistics, and infrastructure inspection, the AMCRP holds promise for transforming industries. Further research is crucial to fully unlock its capabilities and maximize its utility across sectors.

Keywords: Robotic Mobility Platform, Adaptable Robots, Advanced Mobility, Hand Gesture, Ease-of-Use

1. Introduction

The Advanced Mobility Control Robotic Platform (AMCRP) stands as a groundbreaking advancement in response to the evolving demands of technology across various industries. Engineered to excel in versatility and performance, the AMCRP navigates diverse environments effortlessly, employing advanced mobility solutions such as multi-legged, tracked, or wheeled locomotion. Its modular design seamlessly accommodates various attachments, catering to a wide spectrum of needs across different applications. Complemented by an advanced control system, the AMCRP offers autonomous navigation, remote control, and precise sensor integration, empowering informed decision-making and intervention as required. Its potential applications span logistics, transportation, infrastructure inspection, and environmental monitoring, revolutionizing industries and fostering efficient, safe, and insightful operations.

Hand gesture recognition emerges as a pivotal technology within human-computer interaction, offering flexibility and ease of use. This technology holds promise for facilitating communication among individuals with disabilities and seamlessly controlling devices. By integrating an Arduino Uno and an accelerometer into a hand glove, the hand-gesture control system detects acceleration forces generated by hand movements. The Arduino Uno processes this data, converting it into angle values ranging from 0° to 450°, which are wirelessly transmitted to control the mobility platform via an RF receiver. This innovative approach bridges the gap between human intention and machine action, exemplifying the potential of gesture-based interfaces in enhancing accessibility and control.

This introduction encapsulates the transformative potential of the AMCRP in revolutionizing industries through its advanced mobility capabilities and modular design. Additionally, it highlights the innovative application of hand gesture recognition technology in empowering individuals with disabilities and enhancing human-computer interaction. Through these advancements, this research aims to contribute to the ongoing evolution of technology-driven solutions for addressing complex challenges and improving the quality of life for individuals across diverse settings.

2. Literature Survey

Borenstein, Johann., et al. "A Mobile Platform for Nursing Robots." (1985)

This paper presents a computer-controlled vehicle developed as part of a nursing robot system at the Technion- Israel Institute for Technology. The platform's design, control algorithms, and sensory devices are discussed, emphasizing its motion control strategy to minimize position errors and slippage. Experimental results on a prototype vehicle are also provided. The platform aims to serve bedridden patients by performing simple tasks like operating appliances or fetching objects, primarily within confined spaces such as hospitals or homes.

Gour, Jagruti P., et al. "Animatronic Hand Using Arduino." (2017)

This paper details the development of a robotic arm utilizing MEMS-ACCELEROMETER technology for gesture recognition. Controlled by preloaded code or a joystick, the arm features six motors for shoulder, wrist, elbow, and gripping movements. The research highlights the implementation of a gesture-recording system using MATLAB and discusses the hand's wireless feedback capabilities. It emphasizes the applicability of the animatronic hand in various fields, including medical, defense, and chemical industries.

Yamano., et al. "Five-fingered Robot Hand using Ultrasonic Motors and Elastic Elements." (2005)

The authors introduce a five-fingered robot hand driven by ultrasonic motors and elastic elements, enabling stable and compliant grasping motion without external power. The hand's components are internally housed due to the compact size of ultrasonic motors. The paper discusses two types of robot hands: built-in actuator type and external actuator type, highlighting their mechanisms and applications in various robotic systems.

Sirisha, P., et al. "Wireless Smart Wheelchair." (2020)

This research presents a voice-controlled wheelchair system utilizing Bluetooth technology and ultrasonic sensors for obstacle detection. Controlled via an Arduino Uno microcontroller and a smartphone application, the wheelchair offers improved mobility and independence for users. The paper discusses the design, implementation, and objectives of the project, emphasizing its potential impact on individuals dependent on wheelchairs.

Mahmood., et al. "Design of a low-cost Hand Gesture Controlled Automated Wheelchair." (2020)

The paper proposes a prototype wheelchair controlled by hand gestures, utilizing Arduino-based microcontrollers and Node MCU. It discusses the system's design, implementation, and additional features such as GPS tracking and emergency switching. The research focuses on providing a simple yet effective solution for wheelchair control, emphasizing accessibility and affordability for users with disabilities.

Razali, Mohd., et al. "Development of Smart Wheelchair System for a User with Severe Motor Impairment" (2012)

This paper introduces a smart wheelchair framework offering manual and semi-autonomous control modes for users with severe motor disabilities. Incorporating safety features and multiple sensors, the wheelchair demonstrates efficient navigation in cluttered environments. The authors discuss future plans for system evaluation and cognitive workload assessment to enhance user experience and reliability.

Chand, J.V. Pavan., et al. "Intelligent wheelchair using voice, touch and gesture control by smartphone." (2021) The research presents an intelligent wheelchair controlled via voice, touch, and gesture commands through a smartphone application. Utilizing Arduino UNO and Bluetooth technology, the wheelchair aims to enhance mobility for individuals with disabilities. The paper discusses the design, implementation, and potential impact of the wheelchair, emphasizing ease of use and accessibility.

Starodubtsev., et al. "Animatronic Hand Model on the Basis of ESP8266." (2019)

This paper introduces an anthropomorphic hand model with a focus on gesture simulation software. The research discusses the development of a debugging prototype and its educational applications in mechanics and animatronics. The stand-mounted hand serves as a training tool for studying motion capture MEMS algorithms and motion mechanics.

Dr. Pushpa D., et al. "IoT Based Smart Wheelchair." (2023)

The study explores the integration of IoT technology into a smart wheelchair system to enhance mobility and user experience for disabled individuals. Highlighting obstacle detection, navigation algorithms, and user-friendly interfaces, the research aims to provide a comprehensive solution for independent mobility. The paper discusses the system design, implementation, and future directions for improving wheelchair accessibility and functionality.

Maheswari., et al. "A Review on Smart Wheelchair Monitoring and Controlling System." (2022)

This review examines current technological advancements in personalized motion devices, focusing on the shortcomings and improvements needed in wheelchair systems. The paper discusses various control mechanisms, including LIDAR-based navigation, haptic feedback, and sensor integration, to enhance wheelchair mobility and safety. Additionally, the review highlights the potential of wearable technologies and wireless communication in smart wheelchair design.

Putri Vidiyarsi D., et al. "Smart Wheelchair Prototype Based Android as A Tool for People with Disabilities." (2019)

The research presents a smart wheelchair prototype controlled via speech recognition and Android-based applications, aiming to enhance mobility for disabled individuals. Utilizing Arduino kit microcontrollers and DC motors, the wheelchair offers wireless control and ease of operation. The paper discusses the system design, implementation, and its potential impact on improving accessibility and independence for users with disabilities.

Al Rakib., et al. "Smart Wheelchair with Voice Control for Physically Challenged People." (2021)

This paper introduces a voice-controlled wheelchair designed to assist individuals with arm and hand impairments. Utilizing Arduino microcontrollers and Bluetooth technology, the wheelchair responds to voice commands for navigation, offering enhanced mobility and independence for users. The research emphasizes the importance of speech recognition technology in overcoming mobility challenges for disabled individuals.

3. Design Inspiration

The design of our robotic platform draws inspiration from the highly regarded AR 250 robotic platform developed by Anscer Robotics. Known for its lightweight transportation capabilities and impressive lifting capacity of up to 250 kilograms, the AR 250 serves as a benchmark in the industry. With its dimensions of 900*580*275mm, the AR 250 offers versatility across various scales of operations.

Incorporating the AR 250's aluminum frame and body construction, our design aims to reduce weight while enhancing structural integrity. Through the reinforcement of the frame and chassis, our robot can support a payload of approximately 400 kilograms, surpassing the capabilities of its predecessor. Additionally, adopting the efficient 2-motor drive system of the AR 250, we prioritize battery longevity to extend operational endurance.

4. Final Design

The finalized design of our robotic platform features an aluminum frame constructed using advanced welding techniques. Laser-cut aluminum sheets are meticulously shaped to match the outer contours of the chassis, providing a sleek and aerodynamic profile. These sheets are securely attached to the frame using a combination of L-clamps, screws, nuts, and rivets.

Figure 2 Frame Design

Figure 1 Final Render

Key design considerations include:

- Prioritization of structural integrity and precision engineering.
- Utilization of aluminum material for its durability and lightweight properties, enhancing overall performance and efficiency.
- Integration of various fastening methods to ensure a robust assembly capable of withstanding operational stresses.
- The overall weight of the frame is approximately 8kg, contributing to a lightweight yet sturdy construction that meets the demands of diverse applications.

5. Simulation

In the pursuit of ensuring structural robustness and reliability, our robotic platform's frame design underwent comprehensive simulation testing, aimed at validating its performance under real-world operating conditions.

1. Load Testing:

The frame design was subjected to rigorous load testing, simulating operational scenarios where the platform carries a maximum load of 4000N, equivalent to 407.88kg. This intensive load testing procedure aimed to assess the frame's capacity to withstand heavy payloads without compromising structural integrity.

2. Structural Integrity:

The results of the load testing revealed that the frame successfully withstood the applied load, showcasing its inherent robustness and resilience. This outcome underscores the frame's ability to endure demanding operational environments and challenging tasks with confidence.

3. Deflection Analysis:

Detailed deflection analysis conducted during testing indicated a maximum deflection of

0.195mm. This minimal deformation under load highlights the frame's exceptional rigidity and stability, essential for maintaining precise motion control and operational efficiency.

4. Simulation Validation:

The test results obtained during load testing provide compelling validation of the accuracy and reliability of the simulation models employed in predicting the frame's performance. This validation process enhances confidence in the predictive capabilities of our simulation methods, reinforcing their utility in guiding design decisions and optimizing structural integrity.

5. Reliability Assurance:

The frame's demonstrated ability to withstand the specified load offers robust assurance of its reliability for real-world applications. This validation instills confidence in the platform's performance and durability, ensuring its suitability for diverse operational scenarios across industries.

By meticulously conducting simulation-based testing and validation procedures, our robotic platform's frame design stands as a testament to engineering excellence, offering a solid foundation for dependable and high-performance operation in practical applications.

Figure 3 Deformation Result

Figure 4 Stress Result

6. Prototyping

A. Components of the prototype

The electronic system integration of our robotic platform encompasses several key components carefully selected to ensure optimal performance and functionality. These components include:

1. Arduino Uno Microcontroller:

The Arduino Uno serves as the central control unit of our robotic platform, facilitating communication between various sensors and actuators. Its versatility, ease of programming, and extensive community support make it an ideal choice for controlling complex robotic systems. The Arduino Uno provides ample input and output pins, allowing for seamless integration of peripheral devices while offering robust processing power to execute control algorithms effectively.

2. ADXL Motion Sensor:

The ADXL motion sensor is a crucial component for enabling motion detection and feedback within our robotic platform. This accelerometer sensor measures acceleration forces in three axes, providing essential data for monitoring the platform's orientation, tilt, and dynamic motion. By integrating the ADXL sensor, our robotic platform can adapt its behavior based on real-time motion inputs, enhancing stability, maneuverability, and overall performance.

3. 500W BLDC Motor Driver:

The BLDC (Brushless DC) motor driver plays a vital role in controlling the propulsion system of our robotic platform. This high-power motor driver is specifically designed to interface with brushless DC motors, offering precise speed and torque control for efficient propulsion. With a power rating of 500W, the BLDC motor driver ensures robust and reliable operation, enabling our platform to navigate diverse terrains and carry heavy payloads with ease.

4. 24V 250W Brushless Hub-Motor:

The 24V 250W brushless motor serves as the primary propulsion source for our robotic platform, delivering ample power and torque to drive its motion. Brushless motors offer several advantages over traditional brushed motors, including higher efficiency, reduced maintenance, and quieter operation. With its compact design and high power output, the brushless motor ensures smooth and reliable locomotion, essential for accomplishing various tasks in dynamic environments.

5. 12V Lead Acid Batteries:

The integration of 12V lead acid batteries connected in series to produce a 24V output provides the necessary electrical energy to power our robotic platform. Lead acid batteries are chosen for their reliability, affordability, and familiarity in the field of robotics. By utilizing lead acid batteries, our platform benefits from a stable power supply capable of sustaining prolonged operation, ensuring uninterrupted performance during missions or tasks.

These integrated electronic components are selected based on their compatibility, reliability, and suitability for the intended application, ensuring that our robotic platform operates efficiently and effectively in diverse environments.

B. Connections

The BLDC hub motors are intricately connected to the BLDC motor driver, encompassing its hall sensor pins, direction, speed, and enable pins, along with power supply connections. The motor driver is seamlessly interfaced with the Arduino Uno board, facilitating program execution and motor control operations. Additionally, the Arduino Uno establishes a vital link with the ADXL motion sensor, strategically embedded within a hand glove worn by the user.

C. Fabrication & Assembly

Before we delve into each step of the fabrication process, it's essential to understand the meticulous craftsmanship involved in bringing our robotic platform to life. Each phase embodies a blend of precision engineering and innovative techniques.

1. Laser Cutting

The fabrication process commences with laser cutting, a precision technique employing a high-powered laser beam to meticulously carve aluminum sheets into precise shapes and dimensions. Renowned for its unparalleled accuracy, laser cutting facilitates the creation of intricate designs while minimizing material wastage. This method proves indispensable in crafting the intricate components essential for the robotic structure and chassis.

2. Aluminum Welding

Next in the fabrication journey is aluminum welding, which involves the fusion of aluminum pieces through specialized techniques such as TIG (tungsten inert gas) or MIG (metal inert gas) welding. Expertise in heat control and fusion is paramount to ensure the formation of robust and durable welds. Welding plays a pivotal role in assembling various parts of the robotic system, ensuring structural integrity and stability essential for optimal performance.

3. CNC Bending

The fabrication process proceeds with CNC bending, leveraging computer-controlled machinery to meticulously shape aluminum sheets into predefined forms and angles with

exceptional precision. Renowned for its repeatability and consistency, CNC bending facilitates the production of uniform components crucial for the robotic system's functionality. This process is instrumental in fabricating structural elements and brackets necessary for mounting diverse components of the robot with precision and reliability.

4. Powder Coating

The final touch in the fabrication process entails powder coating, wherein a dry powder paint is electrostatically applied onto aluminum surfaces before undergoing a curing process under heat. This meticulous coating procedure provides robust protection against corrosion while imparting a visually appealing off-white finish to the robotic system. Beyond its aesthetic enhancement, powder coating ensures the longevity of the robotic system by fortifying it against environmental elements, thus maintaining both functionality and professional appearance over time.

5. Assembly

After the powder coating process, the next crucial step involves meticulously assembling all the fabricated parts together. This intricate process includes joining the frame components, attaching the outer body panels, integrating the batteries, mounting the controller and motor driver, and finally, affixing the motors and wheels. Each component is carefully aligned and secured according to precise specifications, ensuring optimal functionality and structural integrity of the robotic platform. This meticulous assembly phase is critical in realizing the seamless integration of various subsystems, culminating in the cohesive and efficient operation of the robotic system.

Figure 6 Frame

Figure 5 Outer Body

Figure 8 Powder Coating

Figure 7 Assembled Frame

Figure 9 Final Assembly

D. Working

The user dons the glove equipped with the ADXL motion sensor and initiates movement in the desired direction for the robotic platform. As the user maneuvers their hand, the ADXL motion sensor adeptly captures motion data across the X, Y, and Z axes in real-time. This captured motion data is swiftly transmitted to the Arduino microcontroller, where it undergoes meticulous analysis. The Arduino microcontroller meticulously interprets the motion data, discerning the intended direction of movement based on the spatial orientation of the hand.

Upon determining the direction, the microcontroller swiftly generates PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) signals, orchestrating precise motor control actions. These PWM signals are relayed to the motor driver, commanding the BLDC hub motors to engage and propel the robotic platform in the designated direction with remarkable accuracy and responsiveness. Through this seamless integration of sensory input and intelligent motor control, the robotic platform seamlessly translates user gestures into fluid and intuitive motion, ensuring intuitive user interaction and precise maneuverability in diverse operational scenarios.

7. References

1. Borenstein, J., & Koren, Y, A Mobile Platform for Nursing Robots, IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, 32(2), pp.158-165, (1985)
2. Gour, J. P., Shende, J. K., Kubde, K. K., Kothekar, S. K., & Taklikar, P. S., Animatronic Hand Using Arduino. In National Conference on Advances in Engineering and Applied Science (NCAEAS), Vol. 3, Issue 2, pp. 70-73, (2017)
3. Ikuo Yamano Takashi Maeno, Five-fingered Robot Hand using Ultrasonic Motors and Elastic Elements, Proceedings of the 2005 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation Barcelona, Spain, pp.2673- 2678, (2005, April)
4. P Sirisha, Dr Prakash Bethapudi, M Ratna Meghana Naveena, Ch Yamini, Wireless Smart Wheelchair, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), ISSN:2320-2882, Volume.8, Issue 5, pp.1042- 1050, (2020, May)

5. Mahmood, M., Rizwan, M.F., Sultana, M., Habib, M.A., & Imam, M.H., Design of a low-cost Hand Gesture Controlled Automated Wheelchair, 2020 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYMP), pp.1379-1382, (2020)
6. Tomari, M. R., Kobayashi, Y., & Kuno, Y., Development of Smart Wheelchair System for a User with Severe Motor Impairment, pp. 538-546, IEEE, (2012, July)
7. Chand, J.V. Pavan, Ms. Sowmika, Intelligent Wheelchair Using Voice, Touch and Gesture Control by Smart Phone, 4th International Conference on Communication & Information Processing (ICCIP), (2022, July)
8. Starodubtsev, I., Sibogatova, A., Gajniyarov, I., Antipina, I., & Samedov, R., Animatronic Hand Model on the Basis of ESP8266, In International Multi-Conference on Engineering, Computer and Information Sciences (SIBIRCON), (2019)
9. Pushpa, D., Shetty, M. P., Prakruthi, M., Haris, S., & Vijayalakshmi, K., (2023, May), IoT Based Wheel-Chair, International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science (IRJMETS), 5(5), pp.1- 10, (2023, May)
10. Ms. M. Prabha Maheswari, Karthick A, Perumal A, A Review on Smart Wheelchair Monitoring and Controlling System, IJRAR - International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR), E-ISSN 2348- 1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138, Volume.9, Issue 2, pp.49-54, (April 2022)
11. Vidiyari, P. D., Juan, G., Kamaliah, & Jannah, R., Smart Wheelchair Prototype Based Android as A Tool for People with Disabilities, In Proceedings of the First National Seminar Universitas Sari Mulia, NS-UNISM 2019, Banjarmasin, Indonesia: EAI (European Alliance for Innovation), (2020)
12. Rahman, M. A., Abbas F. I., Al Rakib, M. A., Uddin, S., Rahman, M. M., Chakraborty S., Smart Wheelchair with Voice Control for Physically Challenged People, European Journal of Engineering and Technology Research, 6(7), pp.2627-2635, (2021)